

1: Neurodegeneration and Dementia Research

Leveraging data from cohort studies to accelerate medical progress

About 850,000 people in the UK currently suffer from dementia. Dementia is a syndrome causing deterioration in memory, thinking, behaviour, and the ability to perform everyday tasks. While it usually affects older people, it is not a part of the normal aging process. Dementia is one of the main reasons for disability in older people, making them highly dependent upon caregivers, families, and social services. This leads to an estimated socioeconomic cost of over £26 billion a year.

A £53 million collaboration between academia and industry, Dementias Platform UK (DPUK) is working to turn the best dementia research into treatments as quickly and efficiently as possible. The project aims to find ways to delay the onset of dementia, to alleviate its symptoms, to improve the quality of life of the patients, and to slow down or halt the progression of the diseases.

The DPUK portal

The DPUK collaboration is a coordinated way to conduct research in the fields of neurodegenerative disease and dementia. Its aim is to leverage the data gathered in cohort studies, over 30 of which (totalling over 2 million participants) can be accessed through the DPUK portal. Data is shared by the cohort studies using a secure data analysis portal with high levels of ethics and data security. For an overview of the cohort studies involved and details on each of them, the DPUK includes a useful cohort

directory, which provides information on principal investigators and an overview for each study.

Users include both academic researchers and industry stakeholders such as pharmaceutical companies, and the initiative also aims to develop new methods to enhance research in the field. The collaborative approach to data sharing pursued by DPUK is shown by its connections with important national and international stakeholders, including the UK Dementia Research Institute, the European Medical Information Framework (EMIF), the European Prevention of Alzheimer's Dementia Consortium (EPAD), and the Canadian Consortium on Neurodegeneration in Aging (CCNA).

Use of DPUK resources and reach of the program

DPUK is a relatively young initiative, however, its potential for impact is significant. For instance, the £6.9m NIHR-MRC Dementia Deep and Frequent Phenotyping study is currently using DPUK to try to improve the success of clinical trials for treatments in Alzheimer's disease. It involves 250 volunteers from study cohorts in the DPUK collaboration and will perform up to 50 tests that have never been used before to detect dementia, over the course of 12 months. The project participants can be categorised thanks to the data in the DPUK, and include both people at risk of developing Alzheimer's disease and others who are not considered at risk.

The DPUK consortia includes six UK and international companies: Araclon Biotech, MedImmune, GlaxoSmithKline, Ixico, Janssen Pharmaceuticals, and SomaLogic. These companies are especially interested in the detailed health information on 10,000 participants with early-stage dementia, and aim

to conduct novel research in the field of neurodegenerative diseases. This shows how research data management initiatives such as DPUK have the potential to enhance knowledge exchange, and to bring real benefits to the public through collaboration with the private sector.

Title	1: Neurodegeneration and Dementia Research
Subtitle	Leveraging data from cohort studies to accelerate medical progress
Abstract	Dementia and neurodegenerative diseases affect both individuals and society as a whole. However, neither cures nor treatments are available at the moment. The Dementias Platforms UK collaboration aims to turn dementia research into treatments as quickly as possible, to both improve people's lives and decrease the socioeconomic cost related to these types of diseases.
Keywords	dementia; Alzheimer; cohort studies
Research subject area	MEDICAL AND HEALTH SCIENCES
Type of RDM impact/benefit	Efficiency in research and data re-use (e.g., reduce duplication of effort); Socio/Economic impact; Methodological impact (e.g., new approaches developed)
Summary Impact Type	Impact on health and wellbeing
Facts and figures	850,000 people with Dementia, £53 million project (DPUK), £6.9 million project financed using DPUK
Original dataset from which the impact arose	
Maturity of the initiative/data source	Recent (<5 years)
Year (e.g., first data release, first output, year of impact)	2014
Organisations involved	University of Cambridge; Cardiff University; University of Edinburgh; Imperial College London; King's College London; University of Manchester; University of Newcastle; University of Oxford (Academic Lead); Swansea University; University College London
Academic citations	
Links	https://www.mrc.ac.uk/research/facilities-and-resources-for-researchers/dementias-platform-uk/ http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs362/en/ http://www.dementiasplatform.uk/ https://www.mrc.ac.uk/news/browse/world-s-most-in-depth-study-to-detect-early-signs-of-alzheimer-s-disease/ https://www.alzheimers.org.uk/info/20025/policy_and_influencing/251/dementia_uk